

Training Methods in Training of Trainers Programmes: Evidence from a Public, Corporate and Non-Governmental Organization in Zambia

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Abstract

The study explored to examine the training methods used in Training of Trainers (ToT) programmes within selected organizations in Zambia, assessing how these methods align with Knowles' principles of andragogy and broader organizational development needs. Guided by a qualitative convergent design, the research collected data through interviews with supervisors and trainers across three organizations and training observations in Lusaka District. Thematic analysis was employed to identify patterns in how ToT is conceptualized and delivered. The findings revealed that scenario-based learning and on-the-job training were the widely used methods. Their use stemmed from their relevance to real work contexts, cost-effectiveness, and strong alignment with experiential learning principles central to adult education. Although traditional face-to-face instruction remains dominant, organizations have begun integrating blended and digital approaches, a shift accelerated by the disruptions of the COVID-19 pandemic. This transition mirrors global trends toward hybrid learning ecosystems that combine physical and virtual modalities. The study concludes that effective ToT requires a balanced mix of contextually appropriate, adult centered training methods alongside innovative, technology enhanced approaches. It recommends increased investment in training infrastructure and blended learning platforms to strengthen sustainable and responsive ToT practices in Zambian organizations.

Keywords: *Adult Learning, Blended Learning, On-the-Job Training, Scenario-Based Training, Training of Trainers.*

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Introduction

Training of Trainers (ToT) is a capacity-building model designed to equip selected individuals, often supervisors, senior staff, or subject experts with the knowledge, skills, and pedagogical competence needed to train others effectively. Its strength lies in its multiplier effect: trainers become catalysts for disseminating knowledge and skills across entire organizations, communities, or systems (UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning, 2021). Globally, ToT is recognized as a cost-effective and sustainable means of workforce development, particularly in resource-constrained settings where traditional training models may be financially prohibitive (World Bank, 2022). The conceptual foundation of ToT is rooted in adult education theory, underpinned by principles of self-directed learning, learning motivated by relevance, and the use of prior experiences as learning resources (Knowles, 1984).

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In Zambia, ToT has been increasingly integrated into both governmental and non-governmental organizational structures. It is widely practiced across diverse sectors including healthcare, education, agriculture, and community development programs (Mwanza & Phiri, 2020). Similarly, Development partners continue to strengthen Zambia's human resource capacity through various training initiatives, with the World Health Organization implementing a Training-of-Trainers package on community protection for pandemic preparedness and response, while UNICEF and the International Labour Organization contribute to broader capacity-building efforts across health, education, and labour sectors (International Labour Organization, 2021; UNICEF Zambia, 2023; World Health Organization, 2025).

The Zambian labour market faces persistent challenges including skills mismatches, limited access to lifelong learning opportunities, and resource constraints in training delivery (Chisanga & Mweemba, 2021). Lusaka District, as the country's economic and administrative hub, hosts a wide array of organizations that depend on effective training systems to sustain productivity and adapt to changing work demands. ToT programs in this context are critical not only for building technical capacity but also for enhancing leadership capabilities, adaptability, and problem-solving skills among trainers and their trainees (Mwanza & Phiri, 2020). Despite the strategic role of ToT in organizational development, few empirical studies in Zambia have systematically interrogated the training methods used in organizational ToT programs. Studies on ToT in Sub-Saharan Africa and Zambia in particular tend to emphasize program outcomes such as improved productivity or service delivery without interrogating the methods themselves and their theoretical foundations (Mwanza & Phiri, 2020; Nassazi, 2013).

Further, many ToT programmes in organizations select training methods primarily based on availability of resources or cost considerations rather than their alignment with adult learning principles (Chisanga & Mweemba, 2021). This gap in the literature limits the understanding of what makes ToT programs effective if at all and sustainable in environments like the Zambian context. Notwithstanding, organizations increasingly depend on ToT to expand workforce capacity, improve service delivery, and enhance organizational performance. By equipping trainers with the necessary knowledge and pedagogical skills, ToT ensures that training cascades effectively through different levels of the workforce (Mormina, & Pinder, 2018) While ToT is meant to embody experiential and adult-oriented pedagogy, in practice it often reverts to didactic or resource-driven approaches that may not optimize learning outcomes.

Theory of Andragogy

Malcolm Knowles' (1984) theory of andragogy outlines six core assumptions about adult learners that distinguish adult education from pedagogical approaches. Adults need to understand the purpose and relevance of learning (need to know) and view themselves as autonomous, self-directed individuals (self-concept). They draw heavily on their accumulated life and work experiences, which shape how they interpret new information (role of experience) and become ready to learn when confronted with real-life tasks or role demands (readiness to learn). Their learning is problem-centred and oriented toward immediate application rather than abstract content (orientation to learning), and they are primarily motivated by internal factors such as personal growth, job performance, and self-esteem (motivation to learn) (Knowles, Holton & Swanson, 2014; Merriam & Bierema, 2014). These assumptions are directly relevant to this study, as they provide a conceptual lens for analysing how Training of Trainers (ToT) methods in Zambian organizations align with adult learning principles and support effective trainer development.

Andragogy and Design of Training of Trainers

Andragogy offers a useful framework for analysing Training of Trainers (ToT) methods because it highlights why adults respond well to approaches that emphasise autonomy, relevance, and problem-centred learning (Knowles, Holton & Swanson, 2014; Merriam & Bierema, 2014). Empirical studies consistently show that ToT models grounded in adult learning principles lead to higher trainer satisfaction, confidence, and perceived competence (Carboni et al., 2024; Obi-Jeff et al., 2024; Traicoff et al., 2021). Evidence from health-sector ToTs further demonstrates that trainers' skills and knowledge

improve most when training content is closely linked to real work tasks, local context, and opportunities for immediate application (Acharya et al., 2025; Mavropoulos et al., 2019; Traicoff et al., 2021). Such models also strengthen the effectiveness of cascade training by promoting strong facilitation practices, clear trainee expectations, and structured post-training mentorship (Acharya et al., 2025; Luo et al., 2025).

Success of Training of Trainer Programmes

Studies show that successful ToT programmes are those that are generally implemented around a combination of interactive pedagogic methods, starting with context-adapted content and materials, and teaching practice (Jack et al. 2020; Sichula et al. 2022; Willemsen, et al. 2024). The context of implementation cuts across research, education and health to expand skills and knowledge among local expertise and reduce reliance on external trainers (Klassen et al. 2025; Harris et al, 2022). Aligned to this thinking, Mormina and Pinder (2018) observed that the training content alone is not sufficient to the successful implementation of the ToT, the resources, organization alignment and continued support are crucial elements for sustainably cascading ToT programmes in most contexts. Therefore, the sustainable impact of ToT depends largely on context-based designs, coupled with strong institutional support, provision of resources, and strategies to nurture trainers and sustain the cascading of training programmes. However, the gap remains in rigorous long-term evaluations as most ToT programmes tend to be effective at building short-term capacity.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting and Population

The study was conducted in three organizations in Lusaka District, Zambia's administrative and economic centre. Participants included trainers, trainees, and supervisors directly involved in designing, delivering, and overseeing Training of Trainers (ToT) programs, ensuring that data was drawn from individuals with firsthand experience of training methods. Lusaka was selected because of its diverse organizational landscape, relatively well-established training systems, and logistical accessibility. The three participating organizations, one government ministry, one private corporation, and one NGO were chosen for their active ToT programmes operating for at least three years. Organizational identities are withheld to maintain confidentiality.

The study addressed a key gap in existing research: while ToT literature in African contexts has largely focused on training outcomes, little is known about the specific methods used and the extent to which they reflect adult learning principles. Evidence on innovative or context-responsive ToT designs is also limited. By examining training methods rather than outcomes alone, this study contributes new empirical insights and supports efforts to strengthen the relevance and sustainability of ToT in Zambia. The research was guided by the following questions:

1. What training methods are commonly used in ToT programmes in the selected organizational contexts?
2. How do the ToT training methods used in the selected organizations align with adult learning principles?
3. What factors influence the selection of ToT training methods and their perceived effectiveness in achieving training objectives?

Research Design

The purpose of this study was to examine the training methods employed in Training of Trainers (ToT) programmes in Zambia, with particular attention to how these methods reflect adult learning principles and the growing global emphasis on innovative, context-responsive training designs. A qualitative case study design was adopted to generate an in-depth understanding of practice, consistent with the view that qualitative inquiry is well suited to adult education research because it enables exploration of how

individuals interpret and apply their lived experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

The study was guided by an interpretive paradigm, which assumes that social realities such as ToT practices are constructed through participants' meanings and interactions (Schwandt, 2015). This paradigm aligned with the study's aim of understanding how trainers and trainees made sense of the methods they used, why they selected them, and how they perceived their effectiveness within organizational contexts. By foregrounding participants' perspectives, the study sought to illuminate the practical reasoning that shapes ToT method selection in real-world settings.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

Informed by the research design, purposive sampling technique was used to select participants. It was necessary to select the research participants based on specific characteristics or criteria relevant to the research questions (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). For this study, the selection criteria included: (a) current employment as a trainer or supervisor with training responsibilities, (b) at least two years of experience in ToT delivery, and (c) willingness to participate in the study. The study recruited (n=49) participants, training supervisors, trainers and trainees from all the three organizations. The details of the participants from each institution/organisation are presented in table 1 below.

Table 1. Participant Information

		Institution Category		
SN	Participant Category	Government (n)	Private (n)	NGO (n)
1	Training Supervisor	1	1	1
2	Trainer	2	2	2
3	Trainee	12	15	13
Totals		15	18	16

Data Collection

Data were collected through Key Informant Interviews (KII), Focus Group Discussions (FDGs) and observations which lasted between 30 and 45 minutes each. KII were chosen to collect data from Supervisors and trainers because they provide flexibility to explore emerging themes and seek clarifications while ensuring that key issues are covered consistently across all participants (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). FDGs, were used to collect data from the trainees within their respective organizational context and observations were used to observe the ToT methods employed and how they were employed. We conducted three (n=3) FDGs, nine (n=9) KIIs and three (n=3) observations. The questions in both the KII and FGD guides were developed based on the research questions of the study and the theory of andragogy. Both data collection tools included open-ended questions organized around three main themes: (a) training methods currently used in ToT programs, and (b) perceived effectiveness of different methods and (d) challenges and opportunities in ToT delivery.

All interviews were conducted face-to-face at participants' workplaces, scheduled at times that best suited their availability. This setting was intentionally selected to promote participant comfort and to minimize disruption to their daily responsibilities. With informed consent, each interview was audio-recorded to ensure an accurate and comprehensive account of participants' responses. In addition, field notes were taken during and immediately after the interviews to capture non-verbal cues, contextual details, and the researcher's initial reflections.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using inductive thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2019) six-phase framework, selected for its flexibility and suitability for identifying patterned meaning across qualitative datasets. The analysis began with familiarization, during which all interviews were transcribed verbatim and repeatedly read to develop an in-depth understanding of the content and to note preliminary ideas.

The second phase was initial coding. Transcripts were manually coded line-by-line, generating descriptive codes that remained close to participants' own language; this process produced 47 initial codes.

During theme development, related codes were clustered to form potential themes, supported by visual mapping to explore relationships among codes. The fourth phase involved reviewing and refining themes. Candidate themes were checked against the coded extracts and the full dataset to ensure coherence, distinctiveness, and accurate representation of participants' experiences. The fifth phase was about defining and naming themes. Each theme was clearly articulated, and concise labels were developed to capture their core meaning. The final phase was, producing the analysis report, a coherent analytic narrative supported by illustrative quotations that reflected the breadth of perspectives within each theme (Braun & Clarke, 2019) whose details are presented in the finding section.

Trustworthiness

To ensure the rigor and trustworthiness of the study, strategies aligned with Lincoln and Guba's (1985) framework were employed. *Credibility* was strengthened through triangulation by comparing accounts from supervisors, trainers and trainees across the three organizations, as well as through member checking, where preliminary findings were shared with selected participants who confirmed the accuracy of interpretations. *Dependability* was supported by maintaining a detailed audit trail documenting methodological decisions, including the interview guide, and coding framework, enabling potential external review.

Confirmability was enhanced through ongoing reflexive practice. We kept reflexive notes to identify personal assumptions and minimize our influence on data interpretation, while the use of direct participant quotations ensured that findings remained grounded in the data rather than researcher bias. *Transferability* was addressed by providing thick, contextual descriptions of the study setting, participants, and findings, allowing readers to judge the applicability of the results to other contexts (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was granted by the University of Zambia's research ethics board. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who received clear information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and their rights, including the freedom to withdraw at any stage. Anonymity was protected using pseudonyms and the removal of identifying details from transcripts and reports. Confidentiality was ensured by securely storing all data and restricting access to the research team. Participants were also informed that findings would be presented in aggregate form so that individual responses could not be linked to specific persons or organizations

Results and Discussion

The analysis produced three key themes. First, Training of Trainers programs across the three organizations relied primarily on scenario-based training and on the job training. Second, an emerging shift toward blended and digital methods was evident, though still limited. Third, organizational factors such as resource availability, institutional culture, trainer competence, and learner characteristics shaped the selection and application of training methods. The findings that follow expand on each theme by integrating participant perspectives with relevant theory and literature.

Training Approaches Used in ToT Programs

Scenario-Based Training

Participants across all three organizations described scenario-based training as a core component of their ToT programs. This method immersed trainees in realistic, problem-solving situations that closely reflected actual workplace challenges such as customer service dilemmas, interpersonal conflicts, technical issues, and ethical decision making. Trainers valued this approach because it enabled them to observe trainees' reasoning, creativity, and critical thinking skills under pressure. Unlike lecture-based

methods, scenario-based training required active participation and the practical application of knowledge, which participants viewed as central to effective adult learning. The view shared by trainers from three organizations was that:

"There was no single method that guarantees success in every situation, but scenario training makes trainees think outside the box and test different solutions in situations that feel real. They can make mistakes and learn from them without real consequences."

Supervisors similarly valued scenario-based training for its ability to reveal how trainees think and approach problems. One supervisor noted:

"When we use scenarios, we can see not just whether trainees know the right answer, but how they arrive at solutions. We can see their reasoning process, and that tells us a lot about whether they're ready to train others."

Scenario-based training was brought to life through a variety of interactive techniques observed across the three organizations. Trainers commonly used case studies, role-plays, and simulated workplace situations to present trainees with challenges that closely resembled those they would encounter in real operational environments. A typical session began with the trainer introducing a scenario often drawn from an actual incident within the organization followed by time for trainees to analyse the situation individually or in groups. This analytical phase encouraged participants to unpack the problem, consider multiple perspectives, and propose possible courses of action.

Trainers then facilitated structured discussions in which trainees debated alternative responses, justified their reasoning, and reflected on the implications of different decisions. These conversations often revealed the diversity of thought within the group and highlighted the practical complexities of real world problem solving. The sessions concluded with a debrief, during which trainers guided participants to extract key lessons, link their insights to organizational expectations, and connect the scenario to broader principles of effective training practice.

Both the government and private organizations had invested in developing extensive scenario libraries grounded in real events from their operations. This ensured that the training remained highly relevant, context specific, and authentic. The use of these lived examples not only enhanced engagement but also reinforced the credibility of the training, as trainees could immediately recognize the practical value of the situations being explored.

Scenario-based training demonstrates strong alignment with andragogical principles. Scenarios are inherently problem-centered rather than subject-centered, addressing Knowles' emphasis on adults' preference for learning that helps them solve real problems (Sichula, 2022; Yusuf, 2021). They leverage trainees' prior experiences by requiring them to draw on their existing knowledge and skills to analyse situations (Knowles, 1984). Scenarios also respect adult learners' need for autonomy by allowing multiple valid approaches rather than prescribing a single correct solution. One trainer explicitly connected scenario-based training to adult learning principles:

"Adults don't want to just sit and listen. They want to engage with real problems. Scenarios give them that opportunity. They can use their own experience and judgment, and they learn much more deeply than if we just told them what to do."

The effectiveness of scenario-based training identified in this study aligns with wider empirical evidence. Research shows that scenario-driven learning enhances adaptability, teamwork, and problem-solving by requiring learners to navigate ambiguity and generate creative responses (Errington, 2011; Clark, 2013). In African contexts, scenario-based and simulation-based approaches have similarly been shown to strengthen context-sensitive decision-making in resource-constrained sectors such as healthcare and education (ILO, 2021; UNESCO IICBA, 2020; WHO Africa, 2022).

The effectiveness of this method can be understood through several well-established learning principles. First, scenarios promote cognitive engagement by presenting tasks that are challenging yet achievable, keeping learners within Vygotsky's "zone of proximal development," where optimal learning occurs

(Clapper, 2015; Luckin and Du Boulay, 2016). Second, they foster social learning, as collaborative analysis and discussion allow learners to co-construct knowledge in line with socio-constructivist theory (Clapper, 2015). Third, structured debriefing supports metacognitive development by encouraging learners to reflect on their reasoning processes, a practice known to enhance the transfer of learning to new and complex situations (Decker et al. 2013).

The Gains Realised from Scenario-Based Training

Participants highlighted several benefits of scenario-based training. It fostered teamwork and collaborative problem solving, as trainees typically worked in groups to analyse and respond to scenarios. The method strengthened critical thinking skills by requiring trainees to navigate complex and ambiguous situations, and it offered immediate feedback because trainers could observe responses in real time and guide learners accordingly. Participants also noted that scenario-based activities were more engaging and motivating than passive instructional methods.

"Scenarios work well when they're done right, but they take a lot of preparation. You need good scenarios that are realistic and relevant, and you need skilled facilitators who can manage the discussion and help people learn from it. When we rush it or don't prepare well, it doesn't work as well."

The Challenges

Despite these advantages, participants acknowledged several challenges. Scenario based training is resource intensive, requiring significant time, preparation, and facilitator expertise. Developing realistic and contextually relevant scenarios demand deep organizational knowledge and careful design (Pedro et al. 2019; Pimblet et al. 2025). Effective facilitation also requires strong pedagogical skills to balance guidance with learner autonomy and to ensure meaningful reflection (Margalef and Roblin, 2016; Petkov, 2023). Participants cautioned that poorly designed scenarios risk oversimplifying real world complexity or appearing artificial, reducing credibility and learning value. Maintaining authenticity therefore required continuous updating of scenarios to reflect evolving organizational realities. Three supervisors and two trainers said:

"The method is resource-intensive in terms of time and facilitator preparation. Developing realistic, relevant scenarios requires deep understanding of the work context and careful design. Facilitating scenario-based learning requires strong pedagogical skills, as trainers we must guide the discussion without dominating it and help trainees to extract learning from their experiences."

On-the-Job Training

On-the-job training (OJT) emerged as the second prominent training method across all three organizations, described by participants as a practical, immersive form of "learning while doing." Trainees developed skills directly within their training work environments under the close guidance of supervisors and experienced colleagues. OJT took multiple forms, including structured training the trainer sessions, mentoring relationships, rotational placements across departments, and supervised practice of specific training tasks. These approaches allowed trainees to observe expert performance, gradually assuming training responsibility, and receive immediate, context-specific feedback. Participants emphasized that OJT not only built technical competence but also helped trainees internalize training organizational norms, and expectations through direct participation in actual training sessions. A supervisor emphasized the centrality of mentorship in OJT:

"On-the-job training promotes mentorship because trainees learn directly from experts in the field, not just from manuals and lectures. They see how experienced trainers handle real training situations, and they get immediate feedback on their own training performance."

One trainer explained that trainers valued OJT for its authenticity and immediate relevance:

"When you learn on the job, you're dealing with real situations, real clients, real problems. There's no gap between learning and application. You learn something and immediately use it. That makes the learning stick."

We observed that OJT was generally implemented in a structured manner, guided by clearly defined learning objectives and regular check ins between trainees and their assigned mentors. As trainees demonstrated increasing competence, their level of responsibility was gradually expanded to support progressive skill development. For government and private organisation, OJT followed an informal mentoring arrangement in which experienced trainers and colleagues provided ongoing guidance and feedback within the training tasks.

From an andragogical perspective, OJT addresses multiple principles of adult learning. It provides immediate applicability, as learning occurs in the context where it will be used. It respects adult learners' self-direction by allowing them to take increasing responsibility as they develop competence. It leverages prior experience by building on trainees' existing knowledge and skills. It is problem-centered, focusing on real workplace challenges rather than abstract content (Knowles, 1984; Kolb, 1984; Merriam and Bierema, 2014). One trainer explicitly connected OJT to adult learning needs:

"Adults want to see how what they're learning applies to their actual work. With on-the-job training, there's no question about relevance. Everything they learn is directly connected to what they need to do in their job."

The literature strongly supports the effectiveness of on-the-job training (OJT) for developing both technical and experiential competencies. Nassazi (2013) emphasizes that OJT is particularly effective for building technical skills and tacit knowledge. Lankau and Scandura (2007) further shows that OJT promotes personal learning and socialization through mentoring relationships, helping trainees internalize organizational culture and develop a professional identity. Evidence from the African contexts indicates that employees who receive structured OJT report higher job satisfaction, stronger organizational commitment, and improved performance compared to those trained solely through classroom methods (Maleka et al, 2019; Nassazi, 2013). Work based learning is especially effective in low resource settings because it expands access to skills without requiring major investments in new training infrastructure, and it keeps training tightly connected to real labour market needs (World Bank, ILO and UNESCO, 2023). ILO analyses of African TVEIT systems show that workplace embedded learning offers a practical alternative (ILO, World Bank and UNESCO, 2023), where formal training facilities are limited, while joint UNESCO, World Bank and ILO (2023), demonstrates that integrating learning directly into workplaces improves the relevance and responsiveness of skills development to actual job demands.

Key Benefits Identified

Participants reported some advantages of on-the-job training. They emphasized its cost-effectiveness, noting that it requires few additional resources beyond the time and expertise of experienced staff who act as mentors. OJT was also seen as confidence-building, as trainees develop competence gradually within a supportive, real-world environment. Participants highlighted the value of strong mentoring relationships, which often extend beyond formal training and provide ongoing professional support. Rotational placements across departments were said to strengthen inter-departmental collaboration, while the direct integration of learning into daily tasks ensured that new skills were immediately relevant and applicable to organizational needs. A supervisor summarized these benefits:

"On-the-job training is probably our most cost-effective method. We don't need special facilities or expensive materials. We use our own people and our own work as the training ground. And the learning is immediately useful because it's directly connected to what people need to do."

Challenges

However, participants also identified significant challenges in implementing OJT effectively. The quality of learning depends heavily on the mentor's skills and availability. When mentors lack pedagogical preparation or are too busy with their own work responsibilities, OJT can result in inconsistent learning outcomes. There is also a risk that trainees may adopt poor practices if mentors themselves have developed bad habits. One trainer expressed concern about quality control:

"The challenge with on-the-job training is that it's only as good as the person doing the mentoring. If your mentor is excellent, you'll learn excellent practices. But if your mentor has developed bad habits or doesn't really know how to teach, you might learn the wrong things."

Participants emphasized the need for formal preparation of mentors to ensure effective OJT. This includes training mentors in adult learning principles, providing them with structured frameworks for guiding trainees, and ensuring they have adequate time to fulfil mentoring responsibilities alongside their regular work duties.

Comparison of Scenario-Based, and On-the-Job Training

We found that both scenario-based training and OJT complement each other in important ways. Scenario-based training develops critical thinking and problem-solving skills in controlled environments where mistakes have no real consequences (Aydos, 2021; Yu et al., 2023). OJT embeds learning in authentic contexts where trainees must navigate real complexity and ambiguity (Herrington et al, 2013). Together, they reflect andragogical principles and ensure that trainers not only conceptualize effective approaches but also develop the practical competence to implement them. The prominence of these two methods across all three organizations suggests that they address fundamental needs in ToT contexts. Both methods are experiential, engaging trainees actively rather than treating them as passive recipients of information. Both are problem-centered, focusing on real workplace challenges rather than abstract content. Both leverage adult learners' prior experience and provide opportunities for immediate application. Supervisors and trainers rarely mentioned traditional lecture-based methods as primary approaches in their ToT programs. When lectures were used, they were typically brief introductions to new content, followed quickly by more active methods. This pattern suggests that organizations have moved away from purely didactic approaches in favour of more experiential methods, even if this shift has occurred more through practical experience than through explicit application of adult learning theory.

Emerging Trends in Training Delivery

Blended and Digital Learning

Although scenario-based training and OJT remained dominant, participants noted a gradual shift toward digital and blended learning, accelerated by the COVID 19 pandemic. Organizations had begun using WhatsApp groups for trainer communication and support, online platforms for pretraining modules and reference materials, and video conferencing for follow up sessions with geographically dispersed trainees. One trainer described this development:

"COVID forced us to think differently about training. We couldn't bring everyone together in person, so we had to find other ways. We started using WhatsApp to share materials and discuss issues. We used Zoom for some sessions. Now that we're back to in-person training, we're keeping some of those digital elements because they work well."

However, participants indicated that the full adoption of digital training remained limited. Persistent barriers such as unreliable internet, inadequate devices, low digital literacy among some staff, and insufficient organizational investment restricted what could be achieved. As a result, most organizations relied on modest blended models that paired face-to-face delivery with simple digital tools rather than shifting to fully online training. Two supervisors separately shared the view that:

"We would like to do more with technology, but we have to be realistic about what is possible. Not everyone has reliable internet at home. Not everyone is comfortable with technology. So we use it where it makes sense, but we can't rely on it completely."

This cautious and incremental approach to digital integration reflects broader trends identified in the literature. Although interest in digital training is growing across African organizations, uptake remains uneven due to persistent infrastructural and capacity limitations (Janse van Rensburg, and Oguttu, 2022; Sele, et al. 2023). This evidence suggests that blended models combining the flexibility of digital tools with the interpersonal strengths of face-to-face engagement are currently the most viable and effective pathways for digital adoption in such contexts.

Factors Shaping Method Selection within Organizational Contexts

Cost and resource availability: The trainers and supervisors identified multiple factors that influenced their selection of training methods. Cost and resource availability were frequently mentioned, with organizations favouring methods that could be implemented with existing resources.

Relevance to work context: Methods were selected based on how well they addressed actual workplace challenges. Alignment with learning objectives influenced choices, with different methods selected for knowledge acquisition, skill development and attitude change.

Organizational culture: Played a role, with private and non-governmental organizations having strong traditions of mentoring and peer learning while government were more comfortable with structured, formal approaches.

Trainer expertise: All three organizations tended to use methods that their trainers were confident implementing. Finally, learner characteristics influenced choices, with methods adapted based on trainees' prior experience, learning preferences, and comfort with different approaches.

Notably, no supervisor and trainer explicitly mentioned adult learning theory as a factor in method selection, even though their choices aligned well with theoretical principles. This suggests that organizations may be applying adult learning principles implicitly through practical experience rather than through explicit theoretical knowledge. This finding points to an opportunity for professional development that helps trainers articulate the theoretical foundations of their practice and apply theory more systematically to enhance effectiveness.

Conclusion

This study shows that Training of Trainers programs among the selected three organizations rely primarily on scenario-based training and on the job training, both of which align closely with established adult learning principles despite trainers rarely referencing theory explicitly. These methods are valued for their realism, practicality, and capacity to support experiential, problem centered learning, the core tenets of adult learning. Emerging interest in blended and digital approaches indicates gradual innovation, yet infrastructural and resource constraints continue to limit full digital adoption. Overall, the findings underscore the effectiveness of experiential methods already in use, while highlighting opportunities for strengthening theoretical grounding among trainers and expanding blended learning models as organizational capacity improves.

This study contributes to the limited research on Training of Trainers (ToT) in African contexts by providing empirically grounded insights into how Zambian organizations design and implement trainer development practices. The findings demonstrate that effective ToT in resource constrained settings does not depend on advanced technology or specialized facilities, but rather on the deliberate use of experiential, problem centered methods that connect learning directly to workplace realities.

The study concludes that ToT effectiveness is shaped not only by the content delivered but also by the appropriateness and application of training methods. Trainers must select and adapt methods in response to adult learners' needs, organizational contexts, and available resources, while remaining open to emerging digital and blended approaches that may enhance reach and impact as capacity improves.

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Conflict of Interests

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